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Article · July 2009

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PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF IMMIGRATION OPERATION BY DISCRETE EVENT MODELLING AND SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

Discrete event modelling and simulation were used to analyse the performance of immigration operation in Botswana. The relationships between length of queues of immigrants, queuing time, service time and engagement of duty officer were investigated. Data collected by direct observation and clock-timing of processing immigrant request at an inland office on a normal working day was used to determine whether to increase or reduce the number of serving officers to balance the operations. The findings indicated that the system of operation was balanced or fairly matched by 75 % utilization of the officer, average immigrant queuing time of 4.2 min, and required no changes. The pilot study could be replicated at other boarder posts and airports prior to the expected influx of tourists during the 2010 World Cup Football Competition in South Africa.

1. INTRODUCTION

Discrete event modelling and simulation of operations at an inland Immigration Office in Botswana was conducted to investigate the relationship between average queuing time of immigrants and utilization of immigration officer. With the forthcoming 2010 World Cup Football competition in South Africa, the operational performance of Botswana immigration offices would be expected to service a large number of tourists, especially, at the border posts with South Africa.

Modeling, simulation and analysis of a border security system have been conducted to find efficient ways of improving border control by examining the inter-relationships between security structure, major elements, performance and effectiveness [1], and have also been used extensively to study system operations and performance [2, 3].

The main objectives of analysing the performance measures by modeling, and simulation were to determine the service rate, utilization of the officer, and average queuing time of the immigrants; for inferences and decisions to be made regarding whether the system was balanced or not.

The operation of an immigration office is considered to be balanced or fairly matched when the station is not busy and one officer can manage the front desk operations without difficulty or need for support staff. The research focused only on events taking place at the front counter, where clients received servi-

ces from an immigration officer, without addressing events taking place in the back rooms.

2. DISCRETE EVENT MODELLING AND SIMULATION

2.1. Discrete event

In a continuous system, simulation involves solution of a set of equations, but for discrete system modeling, event-based program is adopted [4, 5]. The system of immigration operation was considered as discrete event, because clients requiring services arrived at separate points in time and were served individually.

2.2. Modelling Process

A model of the immigration system was developed to permit valid conclusions to be drawn about the real system. Assumptions concerning the operations were expressed as relationships between arriving times and service times.

2.3. Simulation steps

Figure 1 illustrates the steps adopted for the simulation. The problem formulation was the outcome of concerns raised by stakeholders for improving efficiency of service delivery at Botswana immigration offices, and a pilot case was selected for investigation. The objectives and overall project plan were outlined after considering alternative approaches. The cost of the study, time required to accomplish each phase of the research and

Fig. 1. Steps in simulation [4]

and expected results were set out.

The model conceptualization involved abstraction of the essential features of the problem, selection and modification of basic assumptions that characterized the system, and elaboration, until a useful approximation was attained [6].

The data collection took a large portion of the total time required to perform the simulation, and was initiated at early stages of model building, as required by the objectives of the study [7].

At model translation stage, ARENA simulation software [8] was used for the computer programme, which was evaluated by verif-

ying all input parameters, logical structures and iterative debugging. Validation was performed by determining discrepancies and errors between simulated and actual or true data; and the process was repeated until the accuracy was within acceptable criteria and precision.

Numerical experimentation was performed on the system to determine the length of initialization period, run times, replications, and production runs for analysing the system performance.

The model and program documentations were prepared to optimize the parameters and establish relationships between input parameters and output measures of performance after the implementation.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Immigration station

The station had a small office that served immigrants from South African Development Community. The service point had a single counter managed by one immigration officer. The clients called at the office to apply, renew or extend legal status of stay, by submitting completed application forms and passports for processing. The number of days requested and extensions previously granted were verified, while questions regarding the applications were asked before the extension was granted on discretionary basis, without recourse to the dictates of the application. After the service, the client departed, for the next person to be served.

No service fee was paid for the first 90 days of stay. Thereafter, a fee was charged for number of days required. The processing time, including calculation and payment of fees, was treated as service time.

The service at a time (discrete) was in orderly fashion, for once in a queue, a client would be served. The service times were of random duration, determined by complexity of the request and other information demanded.

3.2. ARENA software

The ARENA software version 3 developed by System Modeling Corp was used in the modelling and simulation [8].

3.3. Data collection

Time distribution measurements were

recorded separately for inter-arrival times and service times by 2 individual persons.

For adoption of the research findings, would-be users were closely linked with the study to ensure implementation of the findings would generate revenue for the tourism sector and improve operational efficiency.

3.4. Input data analysis

The arrival time (t_a) and service time (t_s) were inputs for Microsoft Excel, copied to Notepad, and saved in ARENA folder. The analyzer tool was used to classify the input data for time distribution functions, conduct chi-square tests, and determine sample mean, standard deviation, range and number of time intervals. Normal and Beta time distribution fit, and histogram plots of the data were made.

3.5. Model translation

At the model translation stage, conceptual model was converted into computerized model. The conceptual model was coded first into an operational model of 4 modules (arrival, service, departure and simulation) to develop the computerized model.

Using ARENA software, the mean and standard deviation of input data were entered into the respective modules, and program verification was performed through iterative debugging.

The availability of the officer for service was designated to be < 1 due to official break or stoppage times (i.e. not fully utilized). Also queue accumulation with no officer availability was set as 0 service, which took place before official business at 0800 h and during break periods. The performance of the system, was based on the activities of the serving officer, which did not exceed 100 % for imbalance or instability of overloading and the need for another officer to support the overburdened operation.

3.6. Simulation

The test run was implemented on Pentium PC using ARENA simulation software to provide output data.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Arrival and service times

For objective assessment of system performance, the data covered the times when

both client and officer were present. Lunch and tea breaks were treated as available times since another officer would stand in to provide continuous service.

The time distribution function, chi-square tests, mean and standard deviations, and range intervals of histogram data summary are shown in Table 1 (a). for inter-time arrivals and (b). service times. The corresponding plots of time distribution functions and histograms are shown in Fig. 1 for inter-time arrivals and Fig. 2 for service times.

4.2. Simulation data

The utilization factor obtained by numerical computation was 75.3 % (Table 2). The manual calculation of personnel utilization using total working time of 480 min and total service time of 331 min per day, was 69 % (i.e. $331/480 \times 100$ %).

The high variance of about 6 % between numerical and manual estimations could be associated with precision factors. From queue theory, the arrival time model was a poisson distribution, while the service time model was an exponential distribution, but the service distribution was obtained as beta distribution function from the software. The modeling also assumed no renegeing and that no client left the queue before being served.

The number of immigrants in the queue was small, while the average waiting time in the queue of 4.18 min was not long, and coupled with the officer utilization factor of 75.3 %, the operation was considered balanced.

4.3. Verification and validation

For verification, the model output was compared with the actual operations (real system). No performance comparison was made with another immigration station, such as inland office, border post or airport.

5. DISCUSSION

Performance analysis using discrete event modeling and simulation was carried out to determine relationship between number of immigrants, queuing time, service time, engagement of serving officer, and system operational efficiency.

At utilization of 75.3 % per day, the period for break times could be determined ba-

Table 1. Input data analysis

(a). Time between arrivals		(b). Service time	
Distribution Summary		Distribution Summary	
Distribution:	Normal	Distribution:	Beta
Expression:	NORM (8.56, 4.1)	Expression:	1.5 + 9 * BETA (1.81, 1.76)
Square Error:	0.016057	Square Error:	0.004991
Chi Square Test		Chi Square Test	
Number of intervals	= 6	Number of intervals	= 7
Degrees of freedom	= 3	Degrees of freedom	= 4
Test Statistic	= 1.74	Test Statistic	= 1.26
Corresponding p-value	= 0.635	Corresponding p-value	> 0.75
Data Summary		Data Summary	
Number of Data Points	= 55	Number of Data Points	= 56
Min Data Value	= 1	Min Data Value	= 2
Max Data Value	= 17	Max Data Value	= 10
Sample Mean	= 8.56	Sample Mean	= 6.07
Sample Standard Deviation	= 4.14	Sample Std Dev	= 2.11
Histogram Summary		Histogram Summary	
Histogram Range	= 0.5 to 17.5	Histogram Range	= 1.5 to 10.5
Number of Intervals	= 17	Number of Intervals	= 9

Fig. 1. Histogram and Distribution functions for Inter-arrival Times

Fig. 2. Histogram and Distribution fit for Service Times

Table 2. Simulated values of assessment

Specification	Average	Maximum
Number of officers	1	3
Average queuing time (min)	4.18	20
Utilization of Officer	75.3 %	
Number of clients served	56	

sed on the labour law. The results could also be used to plan for expected increase of tourists inter-arrival times in connection with the 2010 World Cup Football Competition in Sou-

th Africa; and preparedness of the border clearing systems for expected influx of tourists.

The methodology adopted and results obtained were consistent with other related research [1, 5, 9], where a system was deemed to have several stochastic elements. The results indicated that the system needed no adjustment (for the time being) since immigrant queues were short (average of 4 min waiting time per person) and the single serving officer was not fully utilized (at 75.3 %).

Having proved the applicability of modeling and simulation to discrete event analysis, experimentation would be required for evaluating the model for operations of nationwide immigration system at other border posts and airports. The data may not necessarily yield the same trends of results because of system structural differences that demand different modeling approaches [10]. The study was therefore considered as preliminary, and further research will be conducted on special days, such as, end of month and festive seasons for variability in data.

In addition, the analysis tool can be applied to check the performance measures related to waiting time by customers clearing and collecting luggage or baggage, especially for connecting flights.

6. CONCLUSIONS

A preliminary study of Botswana immigration system using modeling and simulation to analyse the operation of a field station was undertaken. The performance measures of

length of queue of immigrants, queuing time, and utilisation of serving officer were analysed. The personnel utilization of 75 %, and average queuing time of 4.2 min per client, indicated the immigration operation system was balanced. Engagement of the serving officer has direct relationship to the length of queues and waiting time of the immigrants.

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Journal of Applied Science & Technology
 ISSN 0855-2215, Vol. 14, Nos. 1 & 2, 2009

Appendix 1. Time between arrivals and service time

Customer number	Arrival time (clock time)	Time between arrivals (min)	Service Time (min.)	Customer number	Arrival time (clock time)	Time between arrivals (min)	Service time (min)
1	08:10	0	4	29	11:29	5	3
2	08:15	5	7	30	11:38	9	9
3	08:17	2	3	31	11:44	6	7
4	08:22	5	8	32	11:59	15	6
5	08:25	3	5	33	12:15	16	8
6	08:30	5	5	34	12:19	4	3
7	08:40	10	8	35	12:27	8	5
8	08:42	2	9	36	12:39	12	7
9	08:49	7	2	37	12:40	1	8
10	08:57	8	4	38	12:49	9	4
11	09:08	11	3	39	12:58	9	9
12	09:15	7	8	40	13:07	9	5
13	09:17	2	5	41	13:17	10	4
14	09:22	5	7	42	13:26	9	3
15	09:36	14	10	43	13:39	13	5
16	09:42	8	6	44	13:51	12	3
17	09:43	1	7	45	14:00	9	6
18	09:50	7	3	46	14:08	8	4
19	09:55	5	7	47	14:20	12	7
20	10:11	16	9	48	14:29	9	6
21	10:28	17	5	49	14:39	10	9
22	10:33	5	6	50	14:54	15	8
23	10:39	6	9	51	15:09	15	4
24	10:48	9	10	52	15:20	11	6
25	10:56	8	8	53	15:31	11	5
26	11:09	13	4	54	15:42	11	7
27	11:19	10	5	55	15:45	3	8
28	11:24	5	7	56	15:59	14	7